

THE INFLUENCE OF THE EXPORT MARKET ENVIRONMENT, COMPETENCIES AND COMPANY CHARACTERISTICS ON EXPORT PERFORMANCE WITH STRATEGY AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE

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ABSTRACT

Cross-border trade refers to different cross-border marketing programs, specifically with regard to product offerings, promotional mixes, prices and distribution channel structures. The marketing mix refers to the combination of product strategy, distribution, promotion, and pricing. This strategy is unique and designed to satisfy the intended market. Companies must determine which countries to enter, how to enter each market segment in a country, how to adjust product prices in each different country, as well as how to align communication or promotion within different cultures. The purpose of this study is to find out the influence of the export market environment, company competence, company characteristics on strategy, find out the influence of the export market environment, company competence, company characteristics on export performance, and the influence of strategies that mediate the influence of the export market environment, company competence, company characteristics on export performance, and the influence of strategy on export performance. The number of respondents in this study is 325 export companies in Central Java and the Special Region of Yogyakarta. The research model used in this study is a cascading structure model and to test the hypothesis an SEM (Structural Equation Modelling) analysis technique is used which is operated through the LISREL program. The result of this study is that the export market environment has a positive and significant effect on the strategy. Company competencies do not have a positive and significant effect on strategy, Company characteristics do not have a positive and significant effect on strategy, Export market environment has a positive and significant effect on export performance, Company competencies have a positive and significant effect on export performance, Company characteristics have a positive and significant effect on export performance, strategies mediate the influence of the market environment export to export performance, the strategy does not mediate the influence of company competence on export performance, the strategy does not mediate the influence between company characteristics on export performance, the strategy has a positive and significant effect on export performance.

Keywords: *Export Market Environment, Company Competence, Company Characteristics, Strategy, Export Performance.*

INTRODUCTION

The reality is that it is difficult for a country to be able to meet all its own needs without cooperating with other countries. This is due to the increasing needs of the community and the increasing number of people (Nurseto, 2012). This reason encourages a country to conduct international trade with other countries (Sitompul, 2023). From a macroeconomic perspective, exports are a form of corporate strategy to internationalize to foreign markets, a country's export expansion can increase the accumulation of foreign exchange reserves, increase employment, increase national productivity, and encourage economic growth (Dahiri, 2022). In the era of globalization like today, the increase in international trade causes exports to become a tool to ensure the survival of companies and achieve competitiveness. The company's export performance is achieved through international marketing to increase revenue and greater productivity (Pham et al., 2017).

Cross-border trade refers to different cross-border marketing programs, particularly with regard to product offerings, promotional mixes, prices and distribution channel structures (MASNAN, n.d.). The marketing mix refers to the combination of product strategy, distribution, promotion, and pricing. This strategy is unique and designed to satisfy the

intended market (Spyropoulou et al., 2018). Companies must determine which countries to enter, how to enter each market segment in a country, how to adjust product prices in each different country, and how to align communication or promotion within different cultures (Joo et al., 2018).

The condition of Indonesia's trade balance in 2020 compared to 2019 increased by 658.72%. This is because Indonesia's exports in 2020 compared to 2019 decreased by -4.23%, but the value of imports decreased significantly, namely -18.91% and the export value was greater than the value of imports (Samson, 2015). It can be seen that although the trade balance shows positive numbers, this is due to the declining value of exports and imports quite large. This data shows that export performance is declining followed by a decline in import performance (Yam, 2020).

Indonesia's Trade Balance, shows that good Export Performance greatly determines the value of Indonesia's trade balance (Kuncoro, 2020). Export performance needs to be supported by a conducive export market environment, good corporate competence, dominant company characteristics and the existence of the right strategy carried out by the Company (Apip Alansori & Erna Listyaningsih, 2020). This is shown by several previous studies that discussed export performance and the variables that affect it. According to (Sudarsono, 2020), export performance can be measured using two dimensions, namely financial performance and strategy effectiveness. Export performance can include decisions to export, the number of markets served, the number of products sold and the value of exports (Darmanto & Dwiyani, 2015). Another study, namely (H. S. Arifin & SE, 2023) found that the export market environment has a positive and significant effect on export performance. (S. Arifin et al., 2022) found that company performance is greatly influenced by environmental turbulence. Wahyudi & Adam (2018) also found that corporate competence has a positive and significant influence on the performance of export entrepreneurs. Another opinion is (Alicia, 2023) stating that export performance is greatly influenced by the competence of the company. But in contrast to the findings (Kurniawan & Rinofah, 2016) it shows a significant relationship between competence and capability, and between capability and export performance, but not between competence and export performance.

According to previous studies, there are still theoretical differences related to the export market environment affecting strategy, including (Nurseto, 2012) by analyzing the influence of the relationship between the export market environment and strategy, it was found that the export market environment greatly affects the company's strategy. Some authors found a positive relationship between the level of intensity of the country's market competition and the level of adaptation in the marketing mix program (Yam, 2020). (Kurniawan & Rinofah, 2016) which in his research found that the export market environment has an insignificant influence on marketing strategy, (Apip Alansori & Erna Listyaningsih, 2020) obtained the result that the environment has a negative and insignificant effect on the Company's strategy.

From the results of previous studies, there are still differences in research results related to the influence between the export market environment, competencies, company characteristics, and strategies on export performance, so it is necessary to conduct in-depth research on this problem.

METHODS

The method used in this study is quantitative. Qualitative is research that emphasizes testing theories through the measurement of research variables with numbers aimed at testing hypotheses (Payadnya & Jayantika, 2018). This research is designed using 'causality' (Didin Fatihudin, 2015). The causality design is intended to explain the existence of a cause effect relationship or a relationship that influences and influences between several concepts or several variables studied (Sa'adah, 2021). In this study, the causal relationship pattern that is

the focus of the research is an independent variable consisting of the Export Market Environment (X1), Company Competence (X2) and Firm Company Characteristics (X3) to the bound variable, namely Export Performance (Y) while in this study there is a mediating variable, namely Strategy (Z) (Ibrahim, 2023).

The population of this study is all Export Companies in Central Java and the Special Region of Yogyakarta that export through the port of Tanjung Mas Semarang. Until the end of 2020, there was a population of one thousand six hundred and sixty-six (1666) export companies in Central Java and Yogyakarta, selected as many as three hundred and twenty-five (325) small to large companies, which produce, distribute, and export directly. According to (Sudarsono, 2020) companies that have assets of less than Rp.200 million and a turnover of less than Rp.1 billion /year for small companies, for medium companies have assets of more than Rp.1 billion - 10 billion and a minimum turnover of Rp.1 billion - 50 billion / year and for large companies have assets of more than Rp. 10 billion and a turnover of more than 50 billion / year.

While the research respondents are people who know the export processes in their companies and determine export policies, the respondents are (Seran, 2020): 1.) President Director / General Manager 2.) Director of Operations / Operations Manager 3.) Marketing Director / Marketing Manager 4.) Commercial Director/Commercial Manager 5.) Export Director / Export Manager. Then in determining the type of sample to be used in this study using Non-Probability Sampling, which is a sampling technique that is not randomly selected. In Non-Probability Sampling, there is a Purposive sampling technique, which is a method of drawing non-probability samples that is carried out with certain considerations (Sugiyono, 2012). The consideration in determining the sample is to determine the size of the sample in each class with a proportional allocation so that the sample taken is more proportional (Dwiastuti, 2017).

Furthermore, the scale used to measure the results of the research is the Likert scale. The Likert Scale is used to analyze using parametric statistics such as ANOVA (analysis of variance) and t-tests. According to (Setyawan et al., 2021) the Likert Scale is also used to measure an attitude, opinion and perception of a person or a group of people about an existing problem (Basuki & Nazaruddin, 2015).

The data collection method for the purposes of this research is taken in two ways, including:

- (1) Field Research is a method carried out by researchers by direct observation of the activities carried out by the company. Field studies include observations and questionnaires.
- (2) Literature, namely conducting literature reviews in the form of journals, articles, text books, government regulations and laws that are used as study materials and reference sources in this study (Purnomo, 2016). Meanwhile, the data testing of each variable uses the SPSS (Statistical Product and Service Solutions) software program for windows Release 25.0 and Lisrel 9 (Seran, 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result

The causal relationship of the variables of the export market environment, company competence, and company characteristics to the Strategy can be described as follows:

- 1) The Influence of the Export Market Environment on Strategy.

The value of the path coefficient is 0.44 with a tvalue of $3.97 > 1.96$, so it can be said to be positive and significant. The magnitude of the path coefficient shows that the magnitude of the direct influence of the export market environment on the strategy is 0.44. It means that the export market environment with indicators (Competitive Competition, Government Policy, Exchange Rate Changes, Environmental Turbulence, Environmental Competition) has a

positive and significant effect on the strategy with indicators (Market Selection, Product Strategy, promotion, price, market research). Thus, the export market environment has a positive and significant effect on the accepted strategy.

2) The Influence of Company Competence on Strategy.

It can be seen that the magnitude of the path coefficient to the strategy is 0.40 with a tvalue of $1.39 < 1.96$, so it can be said to be insignificant. The magnitude of the path coefficient shows that the magnitude of the direct influence of competence on the strategy is 0.40. In this study, it turned out that the value of the path and strategy coefficient was 0.40 with a tvalue of $1.39 < 1.96$, indicating that the company's competency indicators (Technology Mastery, Export Knowledge, Management Control, Quality, Marketing Competence) did not have a positive and significant effect on the strategy with the indicators (Market Selection, Product Strategy, promotion, price, market research). Thus, the company's competence has a positive and significant effect on the Strategy in this study is not accepted.

3) The Influence of Company Characteristics on Strategy.

It can be seen that the magnitude of the path coefficient to the strategy is - 0.042 with a tvalue of $0.16 < 1.96$, so it can be said to be insignificant. The magnitude of the path coefficient shows that the magnitude of the influence of the company's characteristics directly on the strategy is - 0.042. In this study, it can be seen that the magnitude of the path coefficient to strategy is - 0.042 with a tvalue value of $0.16 < 1.96$ means that the characteristics of the company with indicators (Company Size, Company Commitment, Management Perception Trend, Market Orientation, Company Age) do not have a positive and significant effect on the strategy with indicators (Market Selection, Product Strategy, promotion, price, market research). Thus, the characteristics of companies with a positive and significant influence are not accepted.

4) Environmental Influence on Export Performance.

It can be seen that the magnitude of the variable path coefficient of the export market environment on export performance (export tendency, export marketing representatives, export growth intensity, export barriers, expansion of Territory/Buyer Customers) is 0.43 with a tvalue of $2.70 > 1.96$, so it can be said to be significant. The magnitude of the line coefficient shows that the magnitude of the direct influence of the export market environment on export performance is 0.43. Thus, the export market environment has a positive and significant effect on the export performance received.

5) The Effect of Company Competence on Export Performance.

It can be seen that the magnitude of the coefficient of the competency variable on export performance (export tendency, Export Marketing Representative, Export Growth Intensity, Export Barriers, Expansion of Territory/Buyer Customers) is 1.13 and the tvalue value is $3.21 > 1.96$, so it can be said to be significant. The magnitude of the coefficient of the line shows that the magnitude of the influence of company competence directly on export performance is 1.13. Thus, the company's competence is proven to have a positive and significant effect on export performance or in other words that the results are accepted.

6) The Influence of Company Characteristics on Performance.

It can be seen that the magnitude of the coefficient of the variable variable of company characteristics (Company Size, Company Commitment, Management Perception Trend, Market Orientation, Company Age) on export performance (export trend, Export Marketing Representative, Export Growth Intensity, Export Barriers, Territory Expansion/Buyer Customer) is 0.84 with a tvalue of $2.61 > 1.96$, so it can be said to be significant. The magnitude of the line coefficient shows that the contribution of the company's characteristics directly to performance is 0.84. Thus, the characteristics of the company are proven to have a positive and significant effect on export performance or in other words that the results are accepted.

7) Strategies for Mediating the Influence of the Export Market Environment on Export Performance

It is known that the value of the variable path coefficient of the export market environment to export performance through the strategy is 0.19 with a tvalue value of $2.73 > 1.96$, so it can be said to be significant. The magnitude of the channel coefficient shows that there is an indirect influence of the export market environment on export performance (export tendency, Export Marketing Representative, Export Growth Intensity, Export Barriers, Expansion of Territory/Buyer Customers) of 0.19 through strategy. Thus the strategy mediates the influence of the environment on performance or in other words that the results are accepted. This influence is classified as part mediation, meaning that independent variables are able to directly affect dependent variables without going through or involving mediator variables.

8) Strategies for Mediating the Influence of Competence on Performance.

It can be seen that the magnitude of the coefficient of the competency variable path to performance through strategy is 0.17 with a tvalue of $1.61 < 1.96$, so it can be said to be insignificant. The magnitude of the channel coefficient shows that the magnitude of the indirect influence of competence on export performance (export tendency, export marketing representatives, export growth intensity, export barriers, expansion of territory/buyer customers) is 0.33. Thus, the strategy does not mediate the influence of competence on performance or in other words that the results are not accepted. This influence is classified as part mediation, meaning that independent variables are able to directly affect dependent variables without going through or involving mediator variables.

9) Strategies to Mediate the Influence of Company Characteristics on Performance.

It can be seen that the magnitude of the coefficient of the variable variable of company characteristics (Company Size, Company Commitment, Management Perception Trend, Market Orientation, Company Age) on export performance (export tendency, Export Marketing Representative, Export Growth Intensity, Export Barriers, Expansion of Territory/Buyer Customers) is -0.02 with a tvalue of $0.16 < 1.96$, so it can be said to be insignificant. The magnitude of the line coefficient shows that the contribution of the indirect influence of company characteristics on performance is -0.02 . Thus, the strategy does not mediate the influence of company characteristics on performance or in other words that the results are not accepted. This influence is classified as part mediation, meaning that independent variables are able to directly affect dependent variables without going through or involving mediator variables.

10) The Influence of Strategy on Export Performance.

It can be seen that the magnitude of the coefficient of the strategic variable path to export performance (export tendency, export marketing representative, export growth intensity, export barriers, expansion of territory/buyer customers) is 0.43 with a tvalue value of $3.79 > 1.96$, so it can be said to be significant. The magnitude of the path coefficient shows that the contribution of the direct influence of strategy to performance is 0.43. Thus, the strategy is proven to have an effect on performance or in other words that the results are accepted.

Discussion

The following is an explanation of the discussion in the research that has been carried out with ten hypotheses:

1) The export market environment has a positive and significant effect on the strategy

The results of data analysis with statistical tests prove that the environment affects the strategy of Indonesian export companies. This is evidenced by a calculated t-value of $3.97 > 1.96$ and a coefficient value of 0.44 with a positive direction. The results of this study are in line with the findings (Elseidi & El-Baz, 2016) and (Qureshi & Mian, 2021) in accordance with the findings (Spyropoulou et al., 2018) that the environment has a great influence on

marketing strategies. During the covid 19 pandemic like today, there are many problems faced by Indonesian exporters to carry out export activities, including lockdowns in several countries affecting the time and costs needed for the delivery of health protocol goods which results in an increase in logistics shipping costs, rising logistics costs, scarcity of containers, availability of ship space, mismatch in size and type of containers entering for import and used for export.

2) Company competence has a positive and significant effect on strategy

The results of data analysis with statistical tests did not prove that competence had an effect on the strategy as evidenced by a t-value of $1.39 < 1.96$ and a coefficient value of 0.40 with a positive direction. Insignificant results show an insignificant impact between company competencies on strategy. The results of this study are not in line with the findings (Susanto & Sukarno, 2022) and (Saputri et al., 2018) that competence has a positive and significant effect on the company's strategy.

3) Company characteristics have a positive and significant effect on Strategy

The results of data analysis with statistical tests showed a t-value of $0.16 < 1.96$ and a coefficient value of -0.042 with a positive direction. So it is not proven that the characteristics of the company affect the strategy of Indonesian export companies. The results of this study are in line with (Burgelman, 2020) establishing a negative relationship between the size and intensity of exports, while (Shaukat et al., 2016) concluded that there is no relationship. The results of this study are not in line with the findings (Porter & Kramer, 2017) where the results of the study were obtained that the characteristics of the company had a significant effect on the strategy of the exporting company.

4) The export market environment has a positive and significant effect on export performance

The results of data analysis with statistical tests prove that the export market environment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of export companies as evidenced by a calculated t-value of $2.70 > 1.96$ and a coefficient value of 0.33 with a positive direction. The results of this study are in line with the findings (Al-Ghwayeen & Abdallah, 2018) and (Jamshidi & Moazemi, 2016), (Edeh et al., 2020) who found in their research that the environment has a positive and significant effect on export performance.

5) Corporate competence has a positive and significant effect on export performance

The results of data analysis with statistical tests prove that competence affects export performance in export companies. This is evidenced by a calculated t-value of $3.21 > 1.96$ and a coefficient value of 1.13 with a positive direction. This finding is in line with (Kim & You, 2019) which found that corporate competence has a positive and significant influence on the performance of export entrepreneurs. But in contrast to the findings (Mohsenzadeh & Ahmadian, 2016) and (Siddiqui & Singh, 2021) it shows a significant influence between competence and capability, and between capability and export performance, but not between competence and export performance.

6) Company characteristics have a positive and significant effect on export performance

The results of data analysis with statistical tests prove that company characteristics have a positive and significant effect on export performance in export companies in Indonesia, as evidenced by a calculated t-value of $2.61 > 1.96$ and a coefficient value of 0.84 with a positive direction. The results of this study are in line with the findings (Ilhan Nas & Kalaycioglu, 2016), (Karipidis et al., 2020) and (Kambey et al., 2018) showing that company characteristics have a positive relationship with export performance.

7) The export market environment has a positive and significant effect on performance through the strategy The results of data analysis with statistical tests prove that the strategy mediates the influence of

environment to performance as evidenced by a calculated t value of $2.73 > 1.96$ and a coefficient value of 0.19 with a positive direction. The results of this study are in line with research (Jamshidi & Moazemi, 2016), (Wang & Ma, 2018) and (Taherdangkoo et al., 2017)

which found that the strategic decision process carried out through complex observation of the business environment will be able to improve the performance of the company.

8) Competence has a positive and significant effect on export performance through strategies

The results of data analysis with statistical tests proved that strategies do not mediate the influence of competence on performance. This is evidenced by a calculated t-value of $1.61 < 1.96$ and a coefficient value of 0.17 with a positive direction. This is not in line with Lages et.al (2009) in his research entitled Relationship capabilities, quality, and innovation as determinants of export performance. *Journal of international Marketing*, 17(4), 47-70. Export marketing strategies serve as important internal mediators that bridge the relationship between internal and external factors and export performance. This finding is also contrary to the opinions of, (Mohsenzadeh & Ahmadian, 2016) and (Elitan, 2015). The mediating role of competitive strategies in the effect of firm competencies and export performance. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 36, 456-466. Stated that the company's competence affects export performance through strategy.

9) Company characteristics affect performance through strategy

The results of data analysis with statistical tests proved that the strategy did not mediate the influence of company characteristics on performance, as evidenced by a t-value of $0.16 < 1.96$ and a coefficient value of -0.02 in a negative direction. The results of this study are in line with (Shaukat et al., 2016) and (Elitan, 2015) showing that export marketing strategies are not a strong determinant of performance. In fact, export marketing strategies have not been identified as an intermediary variable in the relationship between the characteristics of a company and the environment and its performance.

10) Strategy has a positive and significant effect on performance

The results of data analysis with statistical tests prove that strategy affects the performance of Indonesian export employees. This is evidenced by a calculated t-value of 3.79 and a coefficient value of 0.43 with a positive direction. The results of this study are in line with the findings (Mikalef & Pateli, 2017) and (Prajogo, 2016), where the study concluded that there is a positive relationship between strategy and export performance.

CONCLUSION

First, the export market environment has a positive and significant effect on the strategy. The results of the study are in accordance with the objectives and the first hypothesis in this study, so that the first hypothesis is accepted. Second, the company's competence does not have a positive and significant effect on the strategy. The results of this study are not in accordance with the goals and the second hypothesis in this study, so the second hypothesis is rejected. Third, the characteristics of the company do not have a positive and significant effect on the strategy. The results of the study are not in accordance with the goals and the third hypothesis in this study, so the third hypothesis is rejected.

Fourth, the export market environment has a positive and significant effect on export performance. The results of the study are in accordance with the objectives and the fourth hypothesis in this study, so that the fourth hypothesis is accepted. Fifth, company competence has a positive and significant effect on export performance. The results of the study are in accordance with the objectives and the fifth hypothesis in this study, so the fifth hypothesis is accepted. Sixth, the characteristics of the company have a positive and significant effect on export performance. The results of the study are in accordance with the objectives and the sixth hypothesis in this study, so the sixth hypothesis is accepted.

Seventh, the strategy mediates the influence between the export market environment on export performance. The results of the study are in accordance with the objectives and the seventh hypothesis in this study, so the seventh hypothesis is accepted. Eighth, the strategy does not mediate the influence between company competence on export performance. The

results of the study are not in accordance with the objectives and hypotheses eighth in this study, so the eighth hypothesis was rejected.

Ninth, the strategy does not mediate the influence between company characteristics on export performance. The results of the study are not in accordance with the goals and the ninth hypothesis in this study, so the ninth hypothesis is rejected.

Finally, the strategy has a positive and significant effect on export performance. The results of the study are in accordance with the objectives and the tenth hypothesis in this study, so the tenth hypothesis is accepted.

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